

Administration of Computer Science Programme in Nigerian Higher Institutions: Challenges and Ways Forwards

Martina Umeora

Administrator, St. Mary Schools Lapai, Niger State.

Email: Sister49martina@gmail.com

Ogunode Niyi Jacob¹

Federal University Wukari, Nigeria

Email: Ogunodejacob@gmail.com

Abstract: The article discussed the challenges facing the administration of computer science programme in the Nigerian higher institutions. Secondary data was used to support the points raised in the article. The secondary data were sourced from print material and online publication by recognized institutions and individual author. There are many challenges facing the administration computer science programme in Nigerian higher institutions. Some of the challenges include; inadequate funding of computer science programme, inadequate computer science lecturers, inadequate ICT infrastructural facilities, brain-drain, strike actions, high cost of internet data and electronic services and high cost of internet data and electronic services. To solve this challenges, this article recommends the following: government should increase the funding of computer science programme in higher institutions, provide adequate ICT infrastructural facilities, ensure stable academic programme employment of more computer science lecturers, the motivation of lecturers to prevent brain-drain and capacity development programme for lecturers and students.

Keyword: Administration, Challenges, Computer, Science Programme, Higher Education

Introduction:

The National Policy on Education (FGN, 2004), defines Higher Education as the Post - Secondary Section of the National education system, which is given of Universities, Polytechnics and Colleges of Technology including courses as are given by the Colleges of Education, Advanced Teachers Training colleges, Correspondence Colleges and such Institutions as may be allied to them. Peretomode (2007) sees higher education as the facilitator, the bedrock, the powerhouse and the driving force for the strong socio-economic, political, cultural, healthier and industrial development of a nation as higher education institutions are key mechanisms increasingly recognized as wealth and human capital producing industries. Bernett (1997) defines higher educational institutions as unique institutions which are differentiated from others in terms of research and its managers are designated as Provost, Rector, and Vice-chancellor. Higher education is the education for the production of manpower and for aiding social, economic and technological development of a country.

The goals and objectives of higher education in Nigeria according to National policy on education (2004) include the following:

¹ Corresponding author

Higher education, including professional education, has the following aims:

- i. the acquisition, development and inculcation of the proper value orientation for the survival of the individual and societies;
- ii. the development of the intellectual capacities of individuals to understand and appreciate the environment;
- iii. the acquisition of both physical and intellectual skills which will enable individuals to develop into useful members of the community;
- iv. the acquisition of an overview of the local and external environments (FGN, 2004)

The National Policy on Education (2004) again stated that higher educational institutions should pursue these goals through Teaching, Research, the dissemination of existing and new information, the pursuit of service to the community; and by being a storehouse knowledge.

Nigerian higher education is the largest in Africa. Noun (2009) submitted that from a global perspective, economic and social developments are increasingly driving the advancement and application of knowledge. Education in general and higher education in particular, are fundamental to the construction of a knowledge economy and society in all nations. The nation looks up to higher education to through its traditional functions of teaching, research and community service to develop manpower and disseminate necessary knowledge that is needed in industry and other sectors. The Nigeria higher education system comprised of universities, polytechnics, and colleges offering programmes in teacher education and agriculture. Higher education is a community of scholars, free to pursue knowledge without undue interference from anywhere. The science programme is one of the major programmes offers in Nigerian higher education.

The programme offers in the Nigerian universities as listed in the BMAS documents were produced for the under-listed academic disciplines:

- i. Administration; Management and Management Technology;
- ii. Agriculture, Forestry, Fisheries and Home Economics;
- iii. Arts;
- iv. Basic Medical and Health Science
- v. Education;
- vi. Engineering and Technology;
- vii. Environmental Sciences;
- viii. Law;
- ix. Pharmaceutical Sciences
- x. Medicine and Dentistry;
- xi. Science;
- xii. Social Sciences;
- xiii. Veterinary Medicine.

Computer science programme in recent times in the Nigerian higher institutions is facing many administrative challenges which range from poor supervision to poor administration. This article is aimed to discuss the challenges facing the administration of computer science programme in the Nigerian higher institutions.

Concept of Science Programme:

Computer Science programme is one of the programmes offered in the Nigerian higher institutions. Computer Science programme is defined as programmes that are mathematical and technological oriented. The computer science programme is also viewed as a programme that is involved in designing software and hardware. The science programme is the programme that is very important to the social-economic and technological development of a nation. The place of Computer science programmes in the development of the social. Economic and technological development cannot be underestimated. Computer science programme also is known as computer science education according to Sherman (2005) computer education provides the capability to solve teaching and learning problems rapidly and accurately than before. The Computer is an effective device for presenting the educational instructional programme. According to McCormick(1993), computers can be used to diversify, develop and improve the teaching and learning. Technological development can only be enhanced among other things through Computer Education. This was the reason why the Federal Government of Nigeria launched the National Policy on Computer Literacy at primary, secondary and tertiary levels of education in 19879 (Infoguidenigeria 2018).

According to infoguidenigeria (2018), the objectives of computer science education include:

- i. To equip the individual or student with a thorough understanding of the concept of the computer to function properly in this technology century.
- ii. Computer Education was perceived as a new instructional system that was designed to improve the quality of teaching and learning.
- iii. To develop a computer literate society in Nigeria
- iv. To facilitate the use of the computer as a teaching and learning tool in all subject areas and to acquaint students with knowledge of computer technology.
- v. To assist students to appreciate the potentials of the computer and its application in various aspects of life and occupation;
- vi. To acquaint the teachers and students with modern scientific knowledge and skills

Computer science education has introduced a lot of changes in our world today and it will continue to do so in the future. The realization of the objectives of computer science education in Nigeria will go a long way in reducing illiteracy and poverty, which are impediments to national development.

Concept of Educational Administration:

Educational administration is the effective application of educational resources in the management of the educational institution for the actualization of the objectives of the educational institution. Nwankwoala (2016), viewed the educational administration as a broad umbrella encompassing a number of processes such as planning, coordinating, controlling and being involved in other management processes and contribute to the formulation of policies. In order to achieve these goals, the head of the educational organization plans carefully various programmes and activities. The educational organization may be a school, college or university. The head organizes these programmes and activities with co-operation from other teachers, parents and

students, motivating them and coordinating the efforts of staff members as well as directing and exercising control over them. The head evaluates the performance and progress of staff in achieving the purpose of the educational programme, provides feedback to them and brings modification in the plans and programmes of the institution when required. The totality of these processes which are directed towards realizing or achieving the purposes of the school is called educational administration. Kalagbor (2017), defined the educational administration as the process of identifying, mobilizing and utilizing scarce human and material resources relevant in education for the purpose of achieving specific educational goals efficiently and effectively. Gift (2018) sees educational Administration is concerned with integrating the appropriate human and material resources that are made available and made effective for achieving the purposes of a programme of an educational institution

According to Kalagbor (2017), the following activities and programmes come under the scope of educational administration at the institutional level:

- i. Deciding the purposes of the institution or school,
- ii. Planning for academic or curricular and co-curricular activities,
- iii. Preparing the time table and the time schedules for various activities,
- iv. Assigning duties and responsibilities to the staff members,
- v. Organizing curricular and co-curricular programmes,
- vi. Directing and motivating the staff of the institution,
- vii. Coordinating by efforts of people to achieve the purpose.
- viii. Exercising control over the staff,
- ix. Conducting periodical reviews about the progress, achievements and failures of the institution,
- x. Taking measures for staff development,
- xi. Maintaining order and discipline,
- xii. Management of materials
- xiii. Management of finance
- xiv. Maintaining records and registers up to date,
- xv. Maintaining human relationships,
- xvi. Supervision of the work of teachers and other employees
- xvii. Giving feedback to the teachers performing well and taking remedial measures for teachers not performing well.

Computer science programme administration is the systematic ways of arranging science resource to implement science programme with the objectives of actualizing the objective of science programme in the educational institutions.

Challenges facing the Administration of Computer Science Programme:

There are many challenges facing the administration science programme in Nigerian higher institutions. Some of the challenges include; inadequate funding of computer science programme, inadequate computer science lecturers, inadequate ICT infrastructural facilities, brain-drain, strike actions, high cost of internet data and electronic services and high cost of internet data and electronic services.

- i. **Inadequate Funding of Computer Science Programme:** Inadequate funding is one of the major problem facing the administration of computer science programme in the Nigerian higher institutions. Annual budgetary allocation for the administration of computer science programme is not adequate. The administration of computer science programme is very cost-intensive. So, more funds are needed to effectively implement a science programme in higher institutions across the country. Udida, Basse, Udofia, & Egbona, (2009) observed that the major issue in educational development is the shortage of funds. One of the most serious problems threatening the survival of the educational systems is that of the dwindling level of public funding in the face of rising demands and hence rising cost of higher education. This shortage of funds affects job performance and the growth of the institution. Higher educational institutions cannot perform optimally without funding. This situation calls for increased fund initiative from both the government and educational stakeholders so as to sustain the tempo and growth of the education industry. The inability of the Nigerian government to objectively accept and implement the 26% funding formula for education recommended by the UNESCO impact negatively on the performance and sustainability of higher education. Okoli, Ogbondah & Ewor,(2016) also submitted that one of the major challenges facing the management of this sector of education is inadequate funding. The budgetary allocation devoted to education has been considered to be grossly inadequate considering the phenomenon increase in students' enrolment and increasing cost, which have been aggravated by inflation. A serious problem confronting Nigerian public university education today is that of the scarcity of fund. Government financial policies on education have therefore been subjected to constant review with the intention of allocating more resources to university education. Many institutions of higher learning in Nigeria were unable to buy ICT facilities, maintain the few ones available and recruit ICT personnel's because of inadequate funding.
- ii. **Inadequate Computer Science Lecturers:** Another problem facing the administration of computer science programme in the Nigerian higher institutions is the challenge of inadequate computer science lecturers. Shortage of qualified teachers in Nigerian universities is well articulated in the reports of the Federal Government's needs assessment of Nigerian public universities carried out in 2012. Data from the NUC revealed that universities experience an acute shortage of teaching staff in computer science and technology-based disciplines, but teaching staff shortage is very acute in disciplines such as law, engineering, medicine and surgery. These shortages are attributed to several reasons, such as poor incentives for serving teachers, inadequate turnout of teachers in these subjects by teacher-training institutions in the country, and the exodus of lecturers to Western countries in search of greener pastures. The reports also disclosed that only about 43 per cent of university lecturers have PhD qualifications. The remaining 57 per cent have qualifications below PhD. Only seven universities have up to 60 per cent of their teaching staff with PhD qualifications. There are universities with fewer than five professors. For instance, the Kano State University of Science and Technology, Wudil, established 11 years ago and has been turning out graduates, has only one teaching staff with a professor ranking and 25 lecturers who are PhD degree

holders. Similarly, the Kebbi State University of Science and Technology, established in 2006, has only two teaching staff in the professor category and five lecturers who have PhD qualifications. The understaffing of universities in Nigeria has serious implications for quality instruction and academic productivity in the institutions. The situation has led to an increasing culture of visiting lecturers in the system. The few available qualified lecturers are recycled as visiting, adjunct, sabbatical and contract lecturers to work in many universities at the same time. Many of them are always on the road travelling from one university town to another and unable to meet their primary obligations with their tenure-employer (Federal Ministry of Education, 2012). In the tertiary level, the subsector of colleges of education experiences a very acute teaching staff shortage in disciplines such as special education and early childhood development, while the polytechnic subsector reported a very acute shortage of teaching staff in health technology. (NEEDS, 2014).

- iii. **Inadequate ICT Infrastructural Facilities:** ICT Infrastructural facilities are very important in the administration of computer science programme. Infrastructural facilities are social capital that every higher institution must have in adequate to be able to implement the science programme effectively. Ogunode (2020) refers infrastructural facilities to include classrooms, offices, exam halls, laboratories, tables, chairs, desks, power supply, water, good roads network, ICT component within the schools etc. Noun (2012) observed that physical plants are required for teaching, learning and research. They include classrooms, laboratories, workshops, staff offices and libraries. Others include hostels (in residential institutions), staff quarters, students and staff recreational facilities, sports and games facilities. They also include roads, electricity and water supplies (UNESCO, 2006). Another challenging factor militating against the deployment of ICT in Nigerian Tertiary institutions is the lack of facilities (Umar, & Rosnaini 2018, Alturise & Alojaiman, 2013). This is evident when compared to other tertiary institutions of the developed world, that Nigeria tertiary institutions lack basic office gadgets and technologies like computer, printers, faxing machines, photocopiers, binders, and projectors not even to talk of internet in most of the institutions particularly Colleges of Education. The dearth of these rudimentary facilities contributes to the challenges facing the placement of ICT in Nigeria tertiary institutions, as no institutions can function effectively in this modern trend of ICT without these facilities. Apart from educational training, these office gadgets and technologies are so much vital and needed to equip students for future office and corporate activities after their studies (Umar & Rosnaini 2018). In a study conducted by Adeosun, (2010) as quoted by Umar & Rosnaini (2018) showed that lack of ICT resources and poor infrastructure prevents full implementation of ICT in Nigerian tertiary institutions. ICT infrastructural facilities support the administration and management of computer science programme. Their availability aid the realization of educational objectives and their inadequacy affects the implementation of teaching, learning, researching and delivering computer education services. It has been observed that inadequate ICT infrastructural facilities are one of the problems facing the many higher institutions in Nigeria.

- iv. **Brain-Drain:** Brain-drain is one of the major factor responsible for ineffective administration of computer science programme in many Nigerian higher institutions. Much academic staff that are supposed to be lecturing and mentoring the students here in Nigeria are leaving every day to abroad for a better job due to poor working condition. Oni (2000) observed that many experienced and young lecturers are fleeing from the frustration of university life into more rewarding and more challenging sectors of the economy and even migrate to oversea countries. The result of the faculty exodus is observed in the quality of graduates that our universities produce. There is a diminishing scope of mentoring junior researchers by seasoned and senior lecturers in Nigeria due to brain drain. Brain drain has led to declining in research outputs from institutions of higher learning in Nigeria vis-à-vis the disappearance of research centres in Nigerian universities. Odetunde (2004) submitted that there was the mass exodus of many brilliant lecturers to the business world and others left Nigeria for better services. Many ICT lecturers have left the country for better offers in abroad.
- v. **Strike Actions:** Strike action by different union groups in the Nigerian higher institutions is another problem preventing smooth administration of computer science programme across the Nigerian higher institutions. Okoli, Ogbondah & Ewor,(2016) observed that it has become a known fact that students across various universities in Nigeria are constantly faced with industrial actions embarked upon by the Academic and Non-Academic Staff Unions of various institutions. The disagreement or lack of understanding between government and unions arising from non-implementation of the agreement reached, often results in a deadlock that usually disrupts academic calendar. As academic activities are suspended for a long period, the students reading abilities fell. Even the previous knowledge acquired is even forgotten by some students. This mostly turns some students into certificates seekers than knowledge seekers. A big challenge to quality higher education in Nigeria is the incessant staff union disputes and subsequent closures of the institutions. Closure of the institutions affects staff productivity and the realization of educational aim and objectives. Romina (2013) cited Asiyai (2005) who provided a catalogue of strikes by the Academic Staff Union of Universities (ASUU) and the Senior Staff Association of Nigerian Universities (SSANU) within fourteen years. She revealed that they were too many strikes, some of which lasted up to six months. Romina,(2013) cited Asiyai (2006) that identified the variables inducing the frequent trade union disputes as poor conditions of service of the staff, non-implementation of ASUU/FGN or SSANU/FGN agreements, lack of autonomy and academic freedom and poor funding. The universities in Nigeria are presently closed down since July 2, 2013, as a result of the failure of the federal government to implement the agreement reached with the academic staff union of universities since 2009, despite all assurances and memorandum of understanding between the two parties. The disruption of academic programmes of institutions of higher learning affects students learning outcomes since lecturers find it difficult to complete the course work. The frequent disputes and strike galore by university staff and students leave students with little or no time to complete both their theoretical and practical work. In most cases, a semester's course work is sandwiched to a few weeks during which lectures are rushed to accommodate the

time lost to strike. This type of academic rush is a big threat to the attainment of quality in higher education in Nigeria (Romina,2013). Science programme needs a stable and conducive environment for effective administration to take place.

- vi. **Poor Literacy of ICT among Lecturer and Students:** Poor ICT literacy among lecturers and students is another challenge facing the administration of computer science programmes in Nigerian higher institutions. Many staff in the Nigerian tertiary institutions are not ICT computer literate and it is disappointing in this modern digital era (Umar & Rosnaini 2018, Idowu, Esere, & Iruloh, (2017). As it is believed that practice makes perfect, most of the lecturers that studied computer application or undergo computer training but without continuous practice is as good as nothing. Umar & Rosnaini (2018) cited Anene, Imam, & Odumuh, (2014) they observed that illiteracy in this current age of ICT boom is really a great threat to any establishment, let alone of an educational institution whereas almost all human activities depend on ICT. It is interesting to note that as ICT is actually more important in tertiary institutions than most organizations. Within Nigerian tertiary institutions, specifically, academic staff needs ICT for their numerous tasks which includes: students' assessments; exams and records, administration for managerial purposes, design and development of tertiary institutions website; and etc. (Umar, & Rosnaini 2018, Beda et al., 2012). Computers cannot operate without electricity even if all the equipment required is present. Many lecturers in Nigerian tertiary institutions have never used computers in their lives as such they are terribly shy when they are confronted with this new technology and the terminology related with using them (Umar & Rosnaini 2018, Ajegbelen, 2016).
- vii. **High Cost of Internet Data and Electronic Services:** The higher cost of internet services and ICT facilities is another factor preventing effective administration of computer science programme in many higher institutions in Nigeria. The high cost of internet data and electronic services is basically the element of ICT usage and value and is one of the challenges of installing ICT in Nigerian tertiary institutions (Umar & Rosnaini 2018, Tongia & Subrahmanian, 2006). American government received a huge amount of dollars from most developing countries for the connection of few megabits per annum due to the fact that it has a stronghold and control of the ICT (Umar & Rosnaini 2018, Tongia & Subrahmanian, 2006). This apparently affects the deployment and full utilization of ICT in these developing countries, of which Nigeria is inclusive. In Nigeria, the high cost of internet data and fast tariff set by internet providers, mostly international companies doing business in the country with the main interest of making profits is among the challenges of ICT deployment (Umar, & Rosnaini 2018). The high cost of getting, replacing, lack of technical support for maintenance of systems, operating, maintaining, installing, and ICT systems, use of unlicensed software, outdated hardware and software systems, are among obstacles of ICT usage as it relates to the higher institutions lecturers ((Umar, & Rosnaini 2018, Balasubramanian et al., 2009).

Ways Forward:

To solve these challenges, this article recommends the following: government should increase the funding of science program in higher institutions, provide adequate ICT infrastructural facilities, employment of more computer science lecturers, motivation of lecturers to prevent brain-drain, capacity development program for lecturers and students.

- i. **Adequate Funding of Computer Science Programme:** For effective administration of computer science programs in Nigerian higher institutions to possible, the government should increase the funding of the science programs. Romina (2013) Government of Nigeria should place a high premium on education by meeting up the recommended 26% educational spending prescribed by UNESCO, to help revitalize the higher education system. An enabling environment should be created for staff through improved conditions of service, provision of basic infrastructures, virtual libraries and information communication technologies, and internet connectivity. Institutions of higher learning in Nigeria should set up internal quality assurance and monitoring of lecture units to enhance good quality delivery.
- ii. **Adequate Infrastructural Facilities:** More infrastructural facilities like modern laboratories for physic, chemistry, biology, and computers, etc. should be provided. If quality is to be enhanced in our nation's universities, the infrastructural base of the system needs to be improved upon. The government should make available enough funds for the rehabilitation of existing facilities. The government should intensify efforts in providing more physical facilities. Corporate bodies, philanthropists, and alumni associations should assist in the provision of these facilities to aid effective teaching-learning activities. There is a need for a serious expansion of physical facilities and equipment to meet the increasing student population. There is a need to take a serious look at the maintenance culture, which is lacking in Nigeria, as this will go a long way to reduce the rate of decay of the existing facilities (Noun, 2011).
- iii. **Employment of more Computer Science Lecturer:** The government should direct school administrators to employ more computer science lecturers in all the higher institutions in the country. Teachers are strong members of educational institutions. The roles of teachers cannot be replaced. Teachers are the implementer of the school curriculum. The government should direct school administrators to employ more academic staff. This will help to improve the quality of education in the country.
- iv. **Motivation of Lecturers:** To prevent brain-drain among the Nigerian academic staff, the government should increase the salaries of lecturers, provide a conducive teaching environment, and improve on their welfare packages. Romina (2013) observed that to improve quality, lecturers, and academic staff should be motivated to make them more dedicated, devoted, and committed, and effective in their jobs. Institutions of higher learning in Nigeria should employ more lecturers to match the students' population. Institutional policies should be revised to ensure that more emphasis is paid on the teaching effectiveness of lecturers for better quality education.

- v. **Stable Academic Calendar:** Maintaining a stable academic calendar is very important for the attainment of computer science programmes in all educational institutions. It promotes the image of the educational institutions and helps to reduce educational wastage in the system. The government and school administrators should always ensure agreement reached with different unions groups within the educational institutions are well implemented as agreed to avoid strike actions in the educational institutions.
- vi. **Capacity Development for Lecturers and Students:** There is a need for training and retraining of ICT lecturers to enable them to cater to the needs of students. The student should also be trained to make effective use of ICT facilities in the school. This training should be a part of training on the use of ICT facilities for students. Competent technical staff should be employed to take adequate care of ICT equipment. The staff should also be trained in the maintenance of ICT equipment.

Conclusion:

The paper discussed the challenges facing the admission of computer science programs in Nigerian higher institutions. This primarily has to do with its significance effective administration of computer science programs and its challenges on the other. Computer science program has been in the Nigerian higher institutions for decades, steadily making progress, however, many challenges were noted in the papers. This study reviewed the concept of educational administration, the concept of computer science program, and the associated challenges and hindrances amongst higher institutions in Nigeria. The study employed the use of secondary data to pinpointed these challenges: inadequate funding of computer science program, inadequate computer science lecturers, inadequate ICT infrastructural facilities, brain-drain, strike actions, high cost of internet data, and electronic services and high cost of internet data and electronic services. To solve these challenges, this article recommends the following: government should increase the funding of computer science program in higher institutions, provide adequate ICT infrastructural facilities, ensure stable academic program employment of more computer science lecturers, the motivation of lecturers to prevent brain-drain and capacity development program for lecturers and students.

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